

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ПРЕКРАЩЕНИЯ УГОЛОВНОГО ДЕЛА И
УГОЛОВНОГО ПРЕСЛЕДОВАНИЯ В СВЯЗИ С ИСТЕЧЕНИЕМ
СРОКОВ ДАВНОСТИ**

**IMPLEMENTATION PROBLEMS OF THE CRIMINAL CASE AND
CRIMINAL PROSECUTION TERMINATION IN CONNECTION WITH
THE EXPIRATION OF THE STATUTE OF LIMITATIONS**

КОЛОГРЕЕВ ВЛАДИСЛАВ ЕВГЕНЬЕВИЧ,

*Белгородский государственный национальный исследовательский университет
НИУ «БелГУ».*

ГУСАКОВА НАТАЛЬЯ ЛЕОНИДОВНА,

*доцент,
Белгородский государственный национальный исследовательский университет
НИУ «БелГУ».*

KOLOGREEV VLADISLAV EVGENIEVICH,

Belgorod State National Research University NRU «BelGU».

GUSAKOVA NATALIA LEONIDOVNA,

*Associate Professor,
Belgorod State National Research University NRU «BelGU».*

Предметом исследования является прекращение уголовного дела и уголовного преследования в связи с истечением сроков давности. Раскрываются проблемы, связанные с практическим применением основания в виде истечения сроков давности в зависимости от особенностей российского уголовного законодательства, а также анализируются распространенные практические ситуации по применению данного основания. В результате предлагается вариант решения проблем, связанных с реализацией прекращения уголовного дела и уголовного преследования в связи с истечением сроков давности.

The subject of the study is the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution due to the expiration of the statute of limitations. The problems associated with the practical application of the foundation in the form of the expiration of the statute of limitations, depending on the specifics of Russian criminal law, are revealed, and common practical situations on the application of this foundation are analyzed. As a result, a solution to the problems associated with the implementation of the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution in connection with the expiration of the statute of limitations is proposed.

Ключевые слова: *сроки давности, процессуальные сроки, реабилитация, нереабилитирующие основания, судебное решение.*

Key words: *statute of limitations, procedural deadlines, rehabilitation, non-rehabilitating grounds, court decision.*

The modern criminal legislation of the Russian Federation is based on the principles of humanism, respect for the rights, freedoms and interests of each individual. The influence of these general legal principles has significantly affected the process of bringing a person

found guilty of committing a crime to criminal responsibility. According to the analysis of the norms of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation (hereinafter the CC of the Russian Federation), it should be argued that Russian criminal legislation, in addition to criminal punishment, acting as the main measure to bring a person to criminal responsibility, provides for a number of special criminal law institutions, which, according to I.A. Podroikina, work to achieve a compromise between positive and negative the results of the implementation of criminal liability [7, p. 144].

We have the right to assert that the institution of releasing a person from criminal liability has had a special impact on the legislative initiative of the State, thanks to which this institution has a number of features reflecting the specifics of national legislation. Such features include a list of established grounds by which the State refuses to apply any criminal law measures against a person who has committed a criminal act. The list of grounds is exhaustive and among the theorists of criminal law there is a conditional division of this list into two groups. If we are talking about exemption from criminal liability in connection with the expiration of the statute of limitations, then this ground is considered to belong to the group of imperative grounds, according to which the decision to release a person from criminal liability must be taken without fail by an authorized person. In Article 78 of the CC of the Russian Federation, the legislator officially fixed the basis we are analyzing, while it is necessary to point out that the article regulates the rules for calculating the end of criminal prosecution of a person depending on the severity of the crime committed by him, establishes requirements for suspending the passage of time and requirements for non-application of the expiration of the statute of limitations to persons who have committed crimes defined by law [3].

However, despite the rules and requirements established in the criminal law, there are a large number of problems with their application in law enforcement activities.

One of the most common problems is errors related to the issuance of a procedural decision on the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution due to the expiration of the statute of limitations at the stage of preliminary investigation. The norms regulating the release of a person from criminal liability are also contained in the norms of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation (hereinafter the CPC of the Russian Federation) [4]. According to the content of Articles 24 and 27 of the CPC of the Russian Federation, the legislator has determined the grounds for refusing to initiate criminal proceedings or for terminating an already initiated case and criminal prosecution in connection with the expiration of the limitation period for bringing a person to criminal responsibility.

Unfortunately, in the process of applying the grounds for the expiration of the limitation period for bringing a person to criminal responsibility, a number of problems, both theoretical and practical, are encountered. In our opinion, a significant theoretical problem is the attribution of the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution in connection with the expiration of the statute of limitations to a non-rehabilitating basis. A non-rehabilitating ground restricts the rights of a suspect or accused person to compensation for damage caused by criminal prosecution. Such an attribution to non-rehabilitating grounds is determined not by law enforcement activities, but by a direct indication of the criminal law, which is contradictory and restricts the constitutional rights of the suspect or accused. In turn, the violation of the rights of persons, whose guilt in committing a crime has not been proven by the bodies conducting the preliminary investigation, occurs. In particular, in practice, it is not uncommon for a preliminary investigation to last for a long period of time, and no evidence of a person's guilt in committing a crime has been received. Accordingly, after the expiration of the statute of limitations, the criminal case and criminal prosecution must be terminated in favor of the suspect or the accused, but it is terminated on non-rehabilitating grounds.

A significant practical problem is the implementation by a suspect or accused person of the requirements provided for in Part 2 of Article 27 of the CPC of the Russian Federation. According to the content of this part of the article, the person conducting the preliminary investigation is obliged to stop criminal prosecution in connection with the expiration of the statute of limitations

for criminal prosecution, if the suspect or accused does not object to this, but if there is an objection, the criminal proceedings should be continued in the usual manner. Often, a suspect or accused is forced to give official consent to the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution, since in case of disagreement, the investigation of the case can be continued, while the period of preliminary investigation.

Before proceeding to the analysis of the opinions of scientists regarding the problems identified in our article, it is necessary to note a number of works, the subject of which is the institution of the release of a person from criminal liability. First of all, our attention was attracted by the scientific work of O.A. Ryzhkova. In her scientific work, the author explores the features of the process of releasing a person from criminal liability, which is presented as the main institution of Russian criminal law. The author rightly notes that the institution of freeing a person from criminal liability can be considered not only as a refusal by the state from inexpedient deprivation of liberty, but also as a way to individualize punishment, which allows to achieve social justice and correction of the person guilty of the crime to the best extent [1, p. 3]. A.V. Naumov and A.G. Kibalnik note that the theoretical understanding of the institution of exemption from criminal liability is the most controversial in the scientific and legal world, therefore, a number of questions regarding the grounds and consequences of applying methods of exempting a person from criminal liability remain unresolved [2, p. 175]. The presented position of the authors is indisputable for us and is easily confirmed by analyzing the key provisions of substantive criminal law.

Returning to the analysis of the identified problems, we would like to draw attention to the fact that the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation has drawn attention to the problem associated with the "endless investigation" after the refusal of the suspect or accused to terminate the criminal case and criminal prosecution due to the expiration of the terms of criminal prosecution. As a result, the decision of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation served as the basis for making changes to the current criminal procedure legislation [5]. It is about making changes to Art. 27 of the CPC of the Russian Federation, according to which the requirement fixed in the independent part 2.2 of the specified article was added to terminate criminal prosecution on a rehabilitating basis after the expiration of the recommended period for conducting a preliminary investigation from the date of expiration of the statute of limitations of criminal prosecution.

The presented decision of the Constitutional Court not only allowed to resolve an important problem of law enforcement, but also to provide the suspect or accused person with additional grounds for appealing the actions of the inquirer, investigator or prosecutor. For example, as A.K. Averchenko and K.B. Ismailova indicate in their scientific work, the accused person now has the possibility of applying the decision of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation in practice by appealing in accordance with the procedure 125.1 of the CPC of the Russian Federation. When considering such a complaint, the court will be obliged to check the legality and validity of the decision to terminate the criminal case, as well as to check whether or not there are grounds for applying the rehabilitation procedure [6, p. 3].

In turn, we would like to draw attention to the fact that judicial practice on the consideration of such complaints is not numerous, as indicated by the authors themselves. The small number of court decisions affects the legality and validity of the application of requirements for the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution after the expiration of the statute of limitations. In particular, in investigative practice, there are often situations when an inquirer or investigator incorrectly determines the period from which it is necessary to calculate the limitation period for bringing a person to criminal responsibility and making a procedural decision to terminate a criminal case and criminal prosecution. It is common for an inquirer or investigator to include procedural deadlines in the course of bringing a person to criminal responsibility, which together makes it possible to significantly increase the duration of the preliminary investigation. Such situations are unacceptable and violate not only the principle of a reasonable period of criminal proceedings, but al-

so the operation of fundamental criminal law institutions, including the right of a person to rehabilitation.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the procedure for applying the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution in connection with the expiration of the statute of limitations for a long period of time had a number of significant legal gaps that contributed to the violation of the rights and interests of suspects or accused persons. Even after making a number of legislative changes to the regulation of this procedure, in practice there are still situations of its application in violation of the basic rules and requirements of criminal proceedings. We believe that the solution to this problem may be an increase in the number of judicial acts regarding the verification of the legality and validity of decisions made by persons conducting a preliminary investigation on the termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution due to the expiration of the statute of limitations. This will allow not only to develop a clear and unified approach to law enforcement, but also to develop recommendations on the application of this procedure in general. In turn, judicial practice can be formed only through the exercise of the right of a suspect or accused to appeal against the decisions of an inquirer or investigator, therefore there is an additional need to ensure the accessibility of participation in the appeal process.

LIST OF LITERATURE

1. Ryzhkova O.A. Grounds for exemption from criminal liability // Concept. 2014. No. 27. pp. 1-6.
2. Criminal law. General part / ed. A.V. Naumov, A.G. Kibalnik. M.: Yurayt Publishing House, 2024. 448 p.
3. The Criminal Code of the Russian Federation dated 06/13/1996 No. 63-FZ (as amended on 06/12/2024) (with amendments and additions, intro. effective from 07/06/2024). URL: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_10699 (date of appeal: 08/04/2024).
4. Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation dated 12/18/2001 No. 174-FZ (as amended on 05/29/2024) (with amendments and additions, introduction. effective from 07/01/2024). URL: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_34481 (date of application: 08/04/2024).
5. Resolution of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 07/18/2022 No. 33-P "In the case of checking the constitutionality of Part Two of Article 27 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation and paragraph "b" of Part one of Article 78 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation in connection with the complaint of citizen V.A. Rudnikov." URL: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_422489 (date of application: 08/04/2024).
6. Averchenko A.K., Ismailova K.B. Features of termination of a criminal case and criminal prosecution on non-rehabilitating grounds // Problems of science. 2023. pp. 1-6.
7. Brilliantov A.V. Exemption from criminal liability, taking into account judicial practice. M.: Prospekt, 2014. 111 p.
8. Criminal law. General part / I.A. Podroikina, E.V. Seregina, S.I. Ulezko. M.: Yurayt Publishing House, 2024. 299 p.

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